

1 **Using the potential of Canadian goldenrod (*Solidago canadensis*) as a functional filler with**
2 **antioxidant activity of low-density polyethylene composites as an example of sustainable**
3 **development of an invasive plant**

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19

20 **Abstract**

21 Novel bio-based low-density polyethylene (LDPE) composites have been manufactured using
22 different Canadian goldenrod (CG) invasive plant parts. Fragmented and ground blossoms
23 (CGB) and mixed leaves and stems (CGSL) were used as fillers introduced by melt mixing into
24 an LDPE matrix at various concentrations (2, 5, 10, 20, 40 wt%). Moreover, the influence of a
25 series of modified fillers based on stems and leaves saturated with an extract made of blossoms

26 (CGSL+E) on LDPE has been verified. The oxidation resistance of composites was enhanced
27 based on the oxidation induction time (OIT) assessment, which increased from 0.5 min for
28 LDPE to 178 min (CGB), 231 min (CGSL), and 140 min (CGSL+E). All composite series
29 formed by compression molding were exposed to UV-light radiation using Xenon lamps and
30 subjected to spectroscopic (FTIR) analysis, color assessment, and mechanical testing.
31 LDPE/CGSL+E composites demonstrated the most favorable mechanical properties after UV-
32 light exposure. In their case, an increase in Young modulus of 360 MPa was observed for the
33 40 wt% sample (PE ~ 180 MPa) and an acceptable decrease in tensile strength of 6.5 MPa
34 compared to the reference LDPE of 9.8 MPa. The study consists of a screening for future
35 research on the use and simultaneous valorization of the invasive plant into functional
36 composite fillers with increased oxidation resistance.

37
38 **Keywords:** waste fillers, composite, low-density polyethylene, antioxidants, invasive plants,
39 *Canadian goldenrod*

41 **Highlights**

- 42 - Canadian goldenrod (CG) invasive plants were valorized as functional fillers.
- 43 - All CG parts (blossoms, stems, and leaves) exhibit strong antioxidant activity.
- 44 - Polyethylene-CG composites show improved OIT and UV-light aging resistance.

46 **1. Introduction**

47 Invasive species are plants, animals, pathogens, and other organisms that are not native to
48 ecosystems and may cause environmental or economic damage or harm human health. In
49 particular, they threaten biodiversity, including reducing the population or eliminating native
50 species through food competition, predating or transmitting pathogens, and disrupting

51 ecosystem functioning (Weidlich et al., 2020). Invasive plants are defined as non-native trees,
52 shrubs, and herbaceous plants spread by artificial factors, mainly related to human activities
53 and globalization processes. Because of their expansive and sudden presence in a new
54 environment, the growth of native plants is often limited, which can negatively impact
55 ecosystem functioning, native vegetation, and wildlife. Their impact on the native biodiversity
56 of almost all of Earth's ecosystems constitutes one of the greatest threats to this diversity
57 (Rejmánek, 2000; Weidlich et al., 2020). Procedures for systemic counteraction and preventive
58 limitation should consider biomass valorization into new and valuable raw materials (Nguyen
59 et al., 2023; Ortega et al., 2021) and not only its disposal by burdening or conversion to
60 bioenergy (Van Meerbeek et al., 2015). Recent years' achievements and the interest generated
61 by polymer composites with fillers of plant origin (Bledzki and Gassan, 1999; Lewandowski et
62 al., 2022; Ortega et al., 2021; Sałasińska et al., 2012; Sałasinska and Ryszkowska, 2013) lead
63 to conclusions about essential estimation of the possibility of using all parts of invasive plants
64 with optimization of their application range (Ortega et al., 2021).

65 The degradation phenomenon related to the oxidation processes of polymer materials is a
66 significant concern in the plastics industry, shortening the life of final products and limiting
67 manufacturing possibilities, including mechanical recycling. Processing in a molten state of
68 thermoplastic polymers involves exposure to high temperatures under oxidizing conditions.
69 Therefore, each forming cycle is associated with the risk of shortening the polymer chains and
70 forming free radicals in the polymer structure. Their presence translates into faster degradation
71 in the operating conditions of the final product, including those induced by radiation (the
72 ultraviolet range of visible light wavelengths) or temperature. Introducing stabilizers into the
73 matrix has become a common practice to increase the resistance of thermoplastic polymers to
74 oxidation in processing conditions and during the life cycle to avoid or limit the deterioration
75 of their aesthetics and mechanical properties. Most of the commonly used stabilizers are

76 petroleum-based synthetic compounds. Recent research indicates the spreading presence of
77 synthetic migrating from polymers light stabilizers in surface waters, which in the long term
78 may constitute a significant problem not only directly affecting human health but also the entire
79 ecosystem (Hahladakis et al., 2018; Maddela et al., 2023). An action that can limit the
80 unfavorable impact of migrating modifiers is replacing them with organic natural compounds
81 of plant origin, revealing antioxidant properties (Dopico-García et al., 2011; Moraczewski et
82 al., 2020). While the use of individual plant varieties and products resulting from their
83 processing is known, the possibilities of producing functional materials, including polymer
84 composites, from unprocessed or low-processed plant parts are still unclear.

85 Climate change and globalization result in noticeable changes in ecosystems, particularly the
86 migration of invasive animal varieties and the appearance of new plant species. Invasive species
87 are plants that do not naturally occur in a given area but are present due to human interference
88 (Sheppard et al., 2006; Zekič et al., 2020). Actions to prevent their uncontrolled spread should
89 lead to their permanent removal and the maximum use of the obtained biomass. A plant whose
90 uncontrolled spread is a significant problem throughout Europe is the Canadian goldenrod (CG,
91 *Solidago canadensis* L.) (Huang et al., 2007; Sheppard et al., 2006; Zandi et al., 2020). This
92 plant, despite its negative impact on local ecosystems resulting from its tremendous expansion
93 and displacement of native varieties, has several beneficial features. The possibility of
94 producing new products from recycled biomass and maximizing its use is an essential step
95 towards a sustainable economy. CG is a plant that can be used to produce fibers and fillers for
96 composite materials, while inflorescences contain significant amounts of essential oils rich in
97 phytochemicals that have antioxidant properties.

98 Despite many years of research and the widespread use of goldenrods in medicine due to many
99 active compounds (Apati et al., 2002; Popowski et al., 2021; Suleymanova et al., 2020), the full
100 potential resulting from their chemical composition has not been fully revealed. In recent years,

101 thanks to a comprehensive analytical approach, research has discovered previously undefined
102 compounds contained in CG (Radusiene et al., 2015; Zekič et al., 2020). A significant amount
103 of phenolic compounds allows to view this plant as a source of biomass, fiber, or active
104 extractives and as a functional fiber used to produce large-scale, sustainable products. In
105 previous works, the phenolic compound content in various goldenrods was considered. For
106 instance, Radusiene et al. (Radusiene et al., 2015) compared the Canadian goldenrod (*Solidago*
107 *canadiens L.*) and the Late goldenrod (*Solidago gigantea Aiton*). They determined by
108 chromatographic assessment rutin, hyperoside, isoquercitrin, chlorogenic acid, and quercitrin
109 content in inflorescences and leaves. The studies showed different contents of individual
110 phenolic compounds with antioxidant activity in leaves and inflorescences. Canadian goldenrod
111 leaves exhibited a higher total flavonoid and phenolic acid content than inflorescences.
112 However, the unknown thermal stability of the compounds, the undescribed compatibility
113 processes, and the ability to migrate these low-molecular-weight compounds into the polymer
114 under high-temperature processing conditions make it necessary to verify the presence of both
115 parts of the plants as active polymer fillers. The only work considering using goldenrod as a
116 filler in polymer composites was described by Liu et al. (Liu et al., 2017). The authors described
117 using ground goldenrod stems as filler for polyethylene composite. The material production
118 procedure includes mechanical fragmentation and surface modification using silane-based
119 coupling agents. The composites were produced and analyzed only in terms of changes in
120 mechanical and physicochemical properties (water absorption), and the authors defined the
121 maximum concentrations allowing for obtaining beneficial functional properties without
122 referring, however, to the properties of unmodified polyethylene. Stark and Matuna's research
123 on UV-light aging of wood-polymer composites (WPC) (Stark and Matuana, 2003) suggests
124 the possibility of intensifying the phenomena of photodegradation of polyethylene intensified
125 by the additional breakdown of lignin contained in wood flour. The introduction of low-

126 processed ingredients or fillers rich in active compounds with antioxidant properties for
127 producing plant-filler-originated composites has additional justification.

128 Considering the need for the conscious valorization of biomass as functional fillers, screening
129 the different plant parts for detailed final applications resulting from its chemical structure and
130 functionalities became necessary. Previous literature has not considered using CG as an active
131 filler with antioxidant properties, allowing for producing "self-stabilizing" composites filled
132 with biomass. This study aims to verify the possibility of using various parts of the CG and the
133 procedures for its processing into functional fillers to modify the polyethylene matrix. The
134 scope of the experiential works included the extraction of blossoms, stems, and leaves and the
135 application of saturation of stems and fibers by extract obtained from blossoms to verify the
136 possible synergistic effect of their impact on the stabilizing ability. The composites prepared by
137 melt processing were assessed in terms of thermal properties (TGA, DSC, OIT), and then the
138 aging procedure was carried out using exposure to Xenon-based UV light. Polyethylene and
139 composites containing three types of fillers were subjected to spectroscopic (FTIR),
140 colorimetric, and mechanical tests. The research clearly showed the beneficial effect of fillers
141 on increasing the stability of LDPE on UV light, with varying effectiveness depending on the
142 filler series used.

143

144 **2. Experimental**

145 ***2.1. Materials and sample preparation***

146 Bio-based low-density polyethylene (LDPE) was selected and processed as a matrix to
147 investigate its properties after thermal oxidation. LDPE was delivered by Braskem (Brazil). The
148 density of bio-polyethylene provided by the manufacturer (LDPE SPB 681 I'm Green[®]) was
149 0.922 g/cm³. The melt flow index of LDPE in the conditions 190 °C/2.16 kg is 3.8 g/10 min.

150 Canadian goldenrod was collected near Trzciel in the Greater Poland Voivodeship (Poland) in
151 September 2023. After harvesting, the blossoms were separated from the stems, and the stems
152 were cut into fragments up to 300 mm using hand tools. The separated materials were left for
153 24 hours, spread out on a polyethylene sheet, and then dried using forced air dryers at 40 °C for
154 48 hours. Then, the stems and leaves were chopped using a Parkside PMH 2400 A1 knife
155 chopper. In the next step, both blossoms and stems and leaves were ground using a Chemland
156 HC-2000V high-speed grinder (32,000 rpm, 2 min) and sieved using a Fritsch Analysette 3 Pro
157 sieve analyzer to a fraction below 400 µm. In this way, two fillers were obtained, i.e., dried and
158 ground blossoms (CGB) and dried and ground stems and leaves (CGSL). The third series of
159 fillers was based on (CGSL) by saturating them with the extract obtained from blossoms
160 (CGSL+E). The procedure for their production was as follows: goldenrod inflorescences (dried
161 and ground) were introduced into a solution of water and methanol in a ratio of 50/50 (w/w)
162 and stirred using a magnetic stirrer (500 rpm, 2 h), after which the solid fraction was filtered
163 out. Dried and ground goldenrod stems and leaves were added to that solution; for every 1 g of
164 material, there was 4 ml of extract. The composition was set aside for 24 h at room temperature
165 and manually mixed. After that, the modified material was spread in PTFE molds and put in a
166 heating chamber at 50 °C for 24 h to evaporate all remaining solvents from stems and leaves.
167 The material was additionally sieved using a sieve analyzer to a fraction below 400 µm.
168 Mixing the composites in the molten state was preceded by weighing portions of LDPE and
169 fillers and drying the weighed portions using a Chemland vacuum dryer at 50 °C for 24 hours
170 before processing. The melt mixing process was carried out using a Brabender Plasticorder with
171 a temperature set of 170 °C and a kneader rotational speed of 30 rpm for 6 min. The materials
172 produced in this way were pressed immediately after the mixing process using a RemiPlast
173 hydraulic press at a temperature of 170 °C at a pressure of 17 MPa and a total pressing time of

174 3 min using a mold in the form of a steel frame with dimensions of the forming space of
175 100x100x2 mm using PTFE foil spacers.

176 The accelerated aging procedure was carried out following the PN-EN ISO 4892-2 standard
177 using the XENTEST-2200 accelerated aging test chamber equipped with a Xenon lamp.
178 Measurements were made at a radiation intensity of 0.51 W/m² for 100 hours, at a control light
179 wavelength of 340 nm, with a black panel temperature (BPT) of 63 °C.

180

181 **2.2. Methods**

182 Lignin, cellulose, hemicellulose, extractives, humidity, and ash content were assessed following
183 standardized protocols. In short, the Klason method, according to the ANSI/ASTM 1997a
184 standard, was used to determine the content of the lignin, which consists of hydrolysis with
185 H₂SO₄ (Proietti et al., 2017). The holocellulose content in the analyzed biomass was
186 investigated by a gravimetric method (Browning, 1967), where acetic acid and sodium chlorite
187 were applied for the sample delignification. Once this sample was obtained, the total cellulose
188 content was determined following ANSI/ASTM 1977b standard. Hemicellulose is defined as
189 the difference between holocellulose and cellulose contents. The content of extractives in
190 analyzed biomass was determined following NREL/TP-510-42619 (Sluiter et al., 2008) and
191 was based on two subsequent extraction processes conducted with ethanol and water,
192 respectively. Three replicas from three different batches were used for all these tests, and the
193 data presented is the arithmetic mean.

194 A free radical scavenging assay based on a 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) solution was
195 used to determine antioxidant activity. A DPPH is a stable organic nitrogen radical; its alcohol
196 solution has a violet color, which fades out in the presence of antioxidants (Aniško and
197 Barczewski, 2023). UV-VIS spectrophotometry was performed to record the color change of
198 preliminary prepared Candian goldenrod extracts. The 50% methanol solution was used as a

199 solvent, and the extraction process was held for 30 min at 50 °C, resulting in extracts with a
200 concentration of 50 g/l, finally diluted with methanol to 1 g/l. In this study, the evaporated
201 extract prepared as a modifier for Canadian goldenrod stems and leaves was also evaluated.
202 The DPPH was dissolved in methanol to obtain a 63 µM solution. Each flask was prepared by
203 adding 0.15 ml of extract and 2.85 ml of DPPH solution. They were then kept closed in the dark
204 for 30 min, after which the absorbance was measured using Spectrophotometer UV-VIS
205 UviLine 9400 at 517 nm. Recorded absorbances were converted to inhibition (1) and then to
206 DPPH radical scavenging capacity (DRSC) expressed in Trolox equivalent. All measurements
207 were performed in triplicate.

208

$$209 \quad IC = \frac{A_{control} - A_{samples}}{A_{control}} \quad (1)$$

210

211 where $A_{control}$ – absorbance value is at 517 nm for the DPPH solution, and A_{sample} – absorbance
212 value is at 517 nm for the tested sample.

213 The second evaluation of antioxidant properties concerns the total phenolic content. This
214 analysis is called the Folin-Ciocalteu method (Rebollo-Hernanz et al., 2021). The same extracts
215 prepared for DPPH assay were used, but their concentration was diluted to 10 g/l with distilled
216 water. To observe changes in solution color the 150 µl of methanolic extract was added into
217 Falcon-type vials and diluted 150 µl of Folin-Ciocalteu reagent with 2100 µl of distilled water;
218 the mixture was left to rest for 3 minutes. After this time, the 750 µl of 20% aqueous solution
219 of Na_2CO_3 was poured into each vial, and the mixture was well homogenized using a vortex
220 stirrer and sat for rest for about 2 h. After this time, the absorbance at 750 nm was measured
221 using The Schott UviLine 9400 UV-VIS spectrophotometer. The obtained absorbances for each
222 sample, measured in triplicate, were expressed as gallic acid equivalent.

223 The total flavonoid content was also determined using the colorimetric method described by
224 Dewanto et al. (Dewanto et al., 2002). Extracts prepared for DPPH assay were also utilized in
225 this method, diluted to a concentration of 5 g/l with methanol. A total of 0.25 ml of the extract
226 was added to vials containing 1.25 ml of distilled water and 75 μ l of a 5% NaNO₂ solution. The
227 mixture was left undisturbed for 5 minutes, after which 150 μ l of a 10% AlCl₃·6H₂O solution
228 was added and allowed to stand for another 5 minutes. Subsequently, 0.5 ml of 1M NaOH and
229 275 μ l of dH₂O were added to achieve a final volume of 2.5 ml. The solution was mixed using
230 a vortex stirrer, and immediately after that, the absorbance was measured at 510 nm against the
231 blank. The spectroscopic examination was performed using UV VIS Spectrophotometer
232 UviLine 9400. The total flavonoid content is expressed as (+)-catechin equivalent for the
233 average of three samples.

234 The fillers and manufactured composites densities were evaluated using the Thermo Fisher
235 Scientific Inc. (Waltham, MA, USA) Pycnomatic gas pycnometer. The measurements were
236 realized at 20 °C using a 40 cm³ measuring cell in an inert atmosphere (helium) at a pressure of
237 0.2 MPa and at the flow direction reference first.

238 The thermal stability of tested materials (components and composites) was evaluated using
239 thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) employing Netzsch TG209 F1 apparatus. The 10±0.2 mg
240 specimens were placed in Al₂O₃ crucibles and heated from 30 °C to 900 °C at 10 °C/min. A
241 Netzsch Proteus software was applied for calculations, including determining the first
242 derivative for obtained TGA data (DTG).

243 Moisture content in the fillers was determined with an Axis BTS 110 moisture analyzer with a
244 temperature set of 105 °C.

245 The scanning electron microscope (SEM) Tescan MIRA3 (Brno, Czech Republic) was used to
246 realize structural analysis. Analysis of the fillers considers their former application to the SEM
247 measuring tables and attachment directly by the conductive tape. All the compression-molded

248 samples were cooled for at least 10 minutes in liquid nitrogen and then broken by impact load,
249 and the cross-section surfaces were analyzed. The evaluated samples were assessed with an
250 accelerating voltage of 12 kV and a working distance of 16 mm. A thin carbon coating of
251 approximately 20 nm thickness was deposited on samples using the Jeol JEE 4B vacuum
252 evaporator.

253 The fillers' particle size was evaluated based on the microscopic image analysis taken by the
254 Opta-Tech MB200s optical microscope connected with the Meiji Techno HD2600T camera.
255 The analyses were made with a magnification of 40x. The particle size results for each series
256 were made for at least 1000 measurements.

257 The thermal properties and indirect assessment of the crystalline structure of polyethylene and its
258 composites were based on the differential scanning calorimetry (DSC). 10 ± 0.2 mg specimens
259 were subjected to a double heating/cooling procedure from -50 to 200 °C at 10 °C/min under
260 nitrogen flow. Measurements were taken for three samples of each series. The measurements
261 were performed with Netzsch 204 F1 Phoenix apparatus and aluminum crucibles with pierced
262 lids. The crystallinity (X_{cr}) of the samples was calculated using formula (2):

$$263$$
$$264 \quad X_{cr} = (\Delta H_m / ((1 - \varphi) \cdot \Delta H_{m100\%})) \cdot 100\% \quad (2)$$
$$265$$

266 where ΔH_m – melting enthalpy of a sample, $\Delta H_{m100\%}$ – melting enthalpy of 100% crystalline
267 polyethylene, $\Delta H_{m100\%} = 293.6$ J/g (Kodjie et al., 2006), φ – filler weight fraction.

268 The oxidation induction time (OIT) of analyzed composites was determined by the differential
269 scanning calorimetry (DSC) analysis. The 5 ± 0.2 mg samples were placed in open aluminum
270 crucibles. They were heated from 20 to 180 °C with a heating rate of 20 °C/min in nitrogen, then
271 kept at 180 °C for 3 minutes in nitrogen, and then gas was switched to oxygen, and the time

272 required for sample oxidation was measured. The measurements were conducted using a Netzsch
273 204 F1 Phoenix apparatus.

274 The Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) measurements were realized using a
275 spectrometer Jasco FT/IR-4600 at room temperature (23 °C) and relative humidity of 30% in
276 a mode of Attenuated Total Reflectance (ATR - FTIR). A total of 64 scans at a resolution of 4
277 cm^{-1} were used in all cases to record the spectra. As part of the signal processing, filtration
278 regarding the influence of H_2O and CO_2 on spectra was used by function of the dedicated Jasco
279 Spectra ManagerTM software. The second derivative method in the OriginPro software was used
280 to deconvolute the carbonyl band. The curve fitting was also carried out in OriginPro software
281 using the Gaussian profile, and the quality of the obtained fitting was controlled by the
282 coefficient of determination ($R^2 > 0.99$). For this evaluation, the FTIR measurement was
283 performed in the wavenumber range 1800 – 1650 cm^{-1} by 64 scans, and the scanning resolution
284 was 4 cm^{-1} . The carbonyl index (CI) based on ATR-FTIR measurements was calculated
285 according to the following equation (Carlsson and Wiles, 1969; Gardette et al., 2013; Yagoubi
286 et al., 2015):

$$287 \quad CI = \frac{A_{C=O}}{A_{CH_2}} \quad (3)$$

288 where: $A_{C=O}$ – the absorbance of a carbonyl group, and A_{CH_2} – the absorbance of the reference
289 peak.

290 Following the ISO 527 standard, the static tensile test investigated the mechanical properties of
291 LDPE and its composites. The tests were performed with 50 mm/min crosshead speed. Flexural
292 properties were measured according to ISO 178 with 10 mm/min bending speed, with 64 mm
293 between cantilevers, determining the elastic modulus and flexural strength. Both measurements
294 were realized employing a Zwick RoellZ010 universal testing machine with a 10 kN nominal
295 force gauge. At least 5 replicates per test for each series were done.

296 The determination of L*a*b chromatic parameters concerning the International Commission on
297 Illumination (CIE) recommendations was used to evaluate the visible changes in the material
298 samples. L*, considered in the range of 0 to 100 (white-black), is interpreted as lightness, a* is
299 color variation between the green and red (- to +) colors at the separate axis, and chromatic
300 parameter b* at the third axis is reflecting color change between the blue and yellow (- to +)
301 (International Commission on Illumination, 1978). A portable spectrophotometer - NR145
302 Precision Colorimeter 3nh (light source D65 and aperture Φ8) was used to measure these
303 parameters. The total color difference parameter (ΔE) was calculated according to the following
304 equation (4) (Latos-Brozio and Masek, 2020):

$$\Delta E = \sqrt{\Delta L^2 + \Delta a^2 + \Delta b^2} \quad (4)$$

307 Additionally, the browning index (Kasim and Kasim, 2015) was obtained according to the
308 following formulas (5) and (6):

$$BI = \frac{100(x-0,31)}{0,17} \quad (5)$$

$$x = \frac{(a^*+1,75L^*)}{(5,645L^*+a^*-0,012b^*)} \quad (6)$$

313 Fig. 1 shows a flowchart showing the process of obtaining and preparing CG-based raw
314 materials, producing composites from them, and their characterization.

317

318 **Fig. 1.** Scheme of manufacturing of CG-filled polyethylene composites.

319 **3. Results and discussion**

320 **3.1. Filler characterization**

321 The chemical composition of three CG-based fillers has been evaluated; Table 1 collectively
 322 presents the results of this investigation. The most distinct difference between CGB and CGSL
 323 fillers may be seen in the cellulose and hemicellulose content, while overall holocellulose
 324 content is comparable. The higher hemicellulose content in the blossoms is mainly associated
 325 with the presence of xyloglucans in seed endosperm in dicotyledonous plant species (Carpita
 326 and Gibeaut, 1993). Moreover, the CGB showed a higher content of extractives soluble in water
 327 and ethanol than CGSL. The modification consisting of saturation of the CGSL with CGB-
 328 extract increased the content of ethanol extractives present in this filler, indicating the
 329 deposition of CGB-originated compounds onto CGSL during soaking. However, the content of
 330 water extractives is reduced as a consequence of such immersion in the water. Immersion in the
 331 extract (CGSL+E) did not change the chemical composition of the CGSL base in the filler, as

332 otherwise expected. Lignin is reported as a component of the lignocellulosic biomass exhibiting
333 antioxidant properties due to the high amount of phenolic groups (Lu et al., 2022). However,
334 the determined lignin content for all three fillers is comparable, so it can be expected that the
335 difference between their impact on the polymer matrix will depend, in this case, on the content
336 of the extractive components. Although this plant species is used in several applications due to
337 its high phenolic and flavonoid content (up to 45% of reported uses are related to its extracts
338 (Zihare and Blumberga, 2017)), its composition in terms of the structural carbohydrates in the
339 biomass is limited. To date, only previous research has been found in the literature reporting
340 them, finding about 35% of cellulose and hemicellulose and 20% of lignin (Kapun et al., 2022).
341 Another study by Aoyagi and Maesono (Aoyagi and Maesono, 2018) reported a lignin content
342 of 22.3% (acid soluble lignin 3.3%; Kalsol lignin 19%) and holocellulose amount of 89.7%
343 (43% α -cellulose; 1.8% β -cellulose), with varied extractives, content-dependent results from
344 medium (0.7% cold water extractives, 6.1% hot water extractives, 27% 1%-NaOH extractives
345 and 0.8% EtOH-benzene extractives).

346 Antioxidant properties of CG plant constituents were evaluated using the DPPH method to
347 assess antioxidant activity and the Folin-Ciocalteu method to obtain total phenolic content.
348 Additionally, the total flavonoid content was evaluated. The antioxidant activity of 50%
349 methanolic extracts is presented as a Trolox equivalent per gram of dry mass (DPPH radical
350 scavenging activity); values of DRSC are placed in Table 1. The extract from CG blossoms
351 exhibits the highest antioxidant activity, followed by the extract from stems and leaves.
352 According to Shelepova et al. (Shelepova et al., 2020), more phytochemicals with antioxidant
353 properties are present within the inflorescence and leaves than stems. Considering that
354 information, the blossom extract was prepared to modify shredded stems and leaves. Soaking
355 them for 24 hours in blossom extract did not cause enhancement of antioxidant activity, and the
356 Trolox equivalent decreased almost two times compared to unmodified material. The

357 immersing stems and leaves in evaporated CGB extract can cause further extraction of water-
358 soluble antioxidant compounds, which did not cause modification with antioxidant compounds
359 after evaporation of water. The increased amount of ethanol extractives and decreased amount
360 of water extractives indicate that the long-term soaking process in aqueous extract leads to the
361 extraction of water-soluble phytochemicals. The extraction of phenol carboxylic acids from CG
362 is higher into water media than the methanol, but the content of the remaining polyphenolic
363 compounds is higher in methanol extraction (Shelepova et al., 2020). The solvent used also
364 affects the total flavonoid content, resulting in higher extraction in methanol solution (Woźniak
365 et al., 2018). To cover all phytochemical extraction, 50% methanol/water solution was used,
366 resulting in a higher total phenolic content and total flavonoid content for blossoms. In the
367 presented study, the total flavonoid content is higher than the phenolic content, but in the
368 literature, it is the other way around (Toiu et al., 2019). In comparison, the extract used for
369 modification of CGSL results in similar TPC and TFC but 1.5 times higher antioxidant activity
370 expressed as Trolox equivalent (149.46 mg/l). The low porosity of biomass may also explain
371 the limited saturation of CGSL with extract rich in antioxidant compounds from blossoms; the
372 low molecular compounds did not have the opportunity to penetrate biomass samples and create
373 a permanent connection.

374 According to Bledzki et al. (Bledzki et al., 2010), the decomposition temperature of the
375 lignocellulosic filler was established as a temperature recorded at 1% mass loss above the value
376 measured at 150 °C by thermogravimetric analysis. The highest degradation temperature was
377 shown by CGSL, which is justified by its chemical composition, with the lowest content of low
378 thermally stable hemicellulose and extractives. The modification decreased the filler's thermal
379 stability, which may be related to the degradation of the extract used to infuse the ground stems
380 and leaves.

381 In the case of unmodified but only ground plant material (CGB, CGSL), the moisture content
 382 from TGA analysis is comparable and close to approximately 7%. Ground CG stems and leaves
 383 treated with blossom extract have a 2% lower moisture content. All materials were tested after
 384 drying and conditioning. CGSL+E reveals the lowest moisture content, and partial
 385 hydrophobization by coating the surfaces of ground plant fragments with small molecular
 386 weight active compounds contained in extracts cannot be excluded. This lower humidity
 387 content for CGSL+E samples was also observed during compositional analyses.

388 **Table 1.** Chemical composition and results of antioxidant activity evaluation of fillers.

Parameter	Unit	CGB	CGSL	CGSL+E
Chemical composition				
Hemicellulose		34.97 ± 8.26	28.89 ± 1.18	29.39 ± 2.19
Cellulose		32.93 ± 1.57	40.31 ± 5.24	41.30 ± 1.51
Kraft lignin		24.10 ± 2.53	22.20 ± 1.49	22.50 ± 3.17
Water extractives	[%]	43.30 ± 3.55	38.41 ± 6.55	30.08 ± 2.10
Ethanol extractives		6.45 ± 2.13	0.12 ± 0.20	2.54 ± 1.07
Ashes		7.10 ± 0.29	5.80 ± 0.33	6.00 ± 0.69
Water content		6.33 ± 0.34	6.92 ± 0.39	4.33 ± 0.26
Antioxidant activity				
Inhibition	[%]	61.67 ± 1.67	43.18 ± 1.25	27.96 ± 1.86
DRSC	[mg/g dry mass]	99.92 ± 2.84	66.46 ± 2.25	38.93 ± 3.37
Total phenolic content				
Gallic acid equivalent	[mg/g dry mass]	42.64 ± 0.24	30.19 ± 0.05	21.52 ± 0.34
Total flavonoid content				
Catechin equivalent	[mg/g dry mass]	56.45 ± 0.16	41.45 ± 0.42	28.93 ± 0.21
Catechin equivalent	[mg/l]	282.25 ± 0.82	207.25 ± 2.09	144.63 ± 1.07
Physicochemical properties				
Density	[g/cm ³]	1.367 ± 0.042	1.402 ± 0.032	1.352 ± 0.012
Decomposition temperature*	[°C]	174.6	197.2	185.1
Humidity	[%]	7.20 ± 0.23	7.77 ± 0.08	5.09 ± 0.10
* According to the procedure described in (Bledzki et al., 2010).				

389

390 Fig. 2 shows the particle size distributions of CG-based fillers. Based on the analysis of Q3 –
 391 cumulative curve dQ3 – density distribution presented as a function of particle size ranges, it
 392 can be found that the filler series containing the largest share of small fractions is CGB. The
 393 increased share of larger particles in the extract-modified series based on fibers and leaves
 394 (CGSL+E) compared to CGSL may result from partial agglomeration of the filler particles. This
 395 effect may also be related to removing the finest fraction of CGSL during the chemical
 396 modification process, which was realized for the ground filler that had already been placed after
 397 grinding.

398
 399 **Fig. 2.** Particle size distribution of CG-based fillers,
 400

401 Fig. 3 shows images of three fillers derived from CG used for research, taken in two
 402 magnifications. Based on the observations, it can be stated that the highest aspect ratio
 403 characterizes dried and ground blossoms (CGB), and a more significant number of fibrous
 404 structures are observed. The CGSL filler obtained from stems and leaves contains a
 405 considerable amount of small filler fractions. After modification with blossoms extract

406 (CGSL+E), the filler shows less fine fraction, which can be attributed to their partial removal
407 during the immersion and modification. This finding aligns with the results of particle size
408 distribution analysis; in the case of the modified CGSL+E series, the share of particles in the
409 $125 < x < 1000 \mu\text{m}$ range is higher than for CGSL. In the images taken with higher magnification
410 (lower row), in the case of CGB and CGSL, a fine structure of the surface of the ground plant
411 material is observed. In the case of the modified CGSL+E material, a change in the surface
412 appearance is observed. It contains more micrometric defects, resulting in a higher surface
413 development. This is probably related to the additional exposure of the filler to methanol, which
414 penetrates the hydrophilic structure of natural fibers, and the subsequent drying, which is
415 included in the modification procedure.

416

417

Fig. 3. SEM images of the fillers in two magnifications.

418

419 The thermal properties of the Canadian goldenrod were evaluated using the thermogravimetric
420 method in an inert atmosphere. Fig. 4 presents mass loss curves and mass derivatives. The
421 thermal decomposition of lignocellulosic materials consists of several steps, three of which
422 indicate degradation of hemicellulose, cellulose, and lignin. To assess an in-depth evaluation of
423 those temperatures, the deconvolution of the DTG peak is necessary. Fig. 5 presents peaks of
424 Canadian goldenrod pyrolysis after deconvolution. The deconvolution process was obtained
425 using OriginPro 9 software with the second derivative method and Lorentz distribution.
426 Canadian goldenrod blossoms showed five degradation peaks, while stems and leaves were
427 characterized by four-step degradation. A detailed description of those steps is presented in
428 Table 2. The first step for each plant material is related to water evaporation. This temperature
429 is similar for all Canadian goldenrod samples. The next step at approximately 220 °C is
430 associated with the decomposition of hemicellulose (Burhenne et al., 2013). After that,
431 degradation of cellulose occurs with a peak at ~280 °C. That kind of low temperature of
432 cellulose degradation indicates the abundance of low molecular weight cellulose; the behavior
433 of cellulose degradation is strictly related to its molecular weight (Calahorra et al., 1989; Huang
434 and Li, 1998). Thermal decomposition of cellulose occurs in a narrower temperature range with
435 greater intensity; deconvolution of DTG peaks showed a narrow peak with high intensity
436 (Kristanto et al., 2021). On the other hand, lignin had a wide range of thermal decomposition
437 with several peaks, mainly three at 270, 310, and 380 °C (Kristanto et al., 2021). In the case of
438 those plant-based fillers, the DTG peaks for lignin are placed approximately at 330 °C and 350-
439 380°C, and the step at 270 °C overlapped with a peak from cellulose degradation. The second
440 lignin degradation peak was not distinguished for solidago stems and leaves. This peak is
441 responsible for secondary pyrolysis reactions cleavage of O-CH₃ bonds accompanied by an
442 aromatic ring (Kawamoto, 2017). This difference can be attributed to higher lignin content in
443 solidago inflorescence. The beginning of thermal degradation is related to hemicellulose

444 content. Canadian goldenrod stems and leaves have the lowest amount of hemicellulose and the
445 highest temperature of the beginning of degradation (197.2 °C), while blossoms (with higher
446 hemicellulose content) start degrading at approximately 175 °C. The chemical modification of
447 stems and leaves did not change significantly the course of pyrolysis compared to unmodified.
448 The $T_{1\%}$ is slightly lower for stems and leaves subjected to soaking in extract; some residual
449 methanol in this solvent may have led to the leaching of hemicellulose components, mainly
450 xylose (Hansen and Plackett, 2008), without changes in overall hemicellulose content (Table
451 1).

453
454 **Fig. 4.** TG and DTG curves of CGB, CGSL and CGSL+E fillers.

456
457 **Fig. 5.** Deconvolution of DTG curves.

460

Table 2. Temperatures of each step of thermal decomposition.

Degradation step	Temperature of DTG peaks [°C]		
	CGB	CGSL	CGSL+E
1	74.6	72.9	77.0
2	223.4	232.9	226.6
3	272.9	276.8	274.3
4	328.1	334.4	330.6
5	416.9	-	-

461

462 *3.2. Evaluation of composites' thermal properties and structure*

463 The structure of polyethylene composites, based on the analysis of brittle fractures obtained
 464 after dynamic loading of samples cooled in liquid nitrogen, was performed using scanning
 465 electron microscopy. SEM images are summarized in Fig. 6 for all material series. Additionally,
 466 pictures taken at higher magnification for the series containing 5 wt% filler to assess the
 467 polymer-filler interphase are presented in the right part of Fig. 6. In the case of highly-filled
 468 composites (>20 wt%), the distribution of fillers was uniform, while the most favorable
 469 distribution of fillers in small diameters in the entire range of composite concentrations was
 470 recorded for the CGB series. Despite the use of the drying process and the high-pressure
 471 compression molding process as part of the procedure for forming test samples, it is possible to
 472 observe discontinuities (pores). What is essential is that there is no noticeable amount of pull-
 473 out holes, which is characteristic of the looseness of the adhesion between the polymer and the
 474 filler. They are only observable for 20% and 40% CGSL+E. Concerning the analysis of the
 475 interfacial area of composites based on SEM images with higher magnification, it can be stated
 476 that in the case of all series of fillers, there are no clear boundaries in the form of gaps in the
 477 interphase within the boundaries of the filler particle. However, a different structure of the fillers
 478 between CGB and CGSL can be observed; in this case, a visible crack in the fracture plane of

479 the CGB filler may indicate its lower strength and ability to withstand mechanical loads. This
480 effect is probably related to the much lower cellulose content in its structure, as shown in Table
481 1.

482

483 **Fig. 6.** SEM images of LDPE and composites cryogenically fractured cross-section.

484

485 The influence of the natural fillers introduced at various concentrations on changes in the
486 thermal properties of composites based on biobased low-density polyethylene was verified
487 using the differential scanning calorimetry. Test results in the form of selected DSC
488 thermograms showing the first cooling and second heating of the materials are depicted in Fig.
489 7. The additional averaged thermal parameters describing the cooling and melting process, i.e.,
490 crystallization (T_C) and melting (T_M) temperatures, with crystallinity determined based on Eq.
491 (2), are collectively presented in Table 3. The introduction of even significant amounts of GR-
492 based fillers did not cause substantial changes in the DSC cooling curves and melting of the
493 polyethylene, and no additional peaks were recorded in the curves. Two exothermic peaks were
494 observed in the range (50-60 °C) and (80-103 °C) in the cooling curves. The recorded
495 exothermic effect in the low-temperature range is related to the presence of crystallites with
496 various thicknesses (Mohammadi et al., 2012). The formation of less stable crystals lower at
497 temperature values is related to branched structure and long chain branches (Mohammadi et al.,
498 2012), characteristic of low-density polyethylene (Shinohara et al., 2019). Polyethylene is a
499 polymer with low susceptibility to heterogeneous nucleation phenomena compared to other
500 polyolefin, such as polypropylene, due to its high crystallization rate and epitaxial
501 crystallization mechanism (Seven et al., 2016; Wittmann and Lotz, 1981). In most reported
502 cases of incorporation of biomass-derived fillers for polyethylene modification (Bouafif et al.,
503 2009; Dolza et al., 2021), as in the considered case, slight changes in the values of characteristic
504 temperatures (T_C and T_M) are observed. However, as for polyethylene, a significant increase in
505 crystallinity caused by the fillers can be observed, especially in the case of the highest CG
506 derivative concentrations. While a small filler content (2%) resulted in a lower X_C compared to
507 the reference sample, the X_C values are noticeably higher for composites containing high filler
508 loadings (20 and 40 wt%) of all filler types based on CG. The most favorable effects were
509 observed for compositions filled with CGSL.

510

511 **Fig. 7.** Selected cooling and second heating DSC thermograms of LDPE and its composites
 512 with CGB, CGSL, and CGSL+E.

513

Table 3. DSC thermal parameters of LDPE and its' composites.

Material	T_c	T_{M2}	X_{C2}
	[°C]	[°C]	[%]
LDPE	$58.2 \pm 0.3 / 94.6 \pm 0.1$	112.9 ± 0.1	46.6 ± 2.3
2% CGB	$57.2 \pm 0.3 / 92.9 \pm 0.5$	114.3 ± 0.5	46.3 ± 3.7
5% CGB	$57.5 \pm 0.6 / 93.5 \pm 0.3$	113.6 ± 0.2	47.7 ± 2.7
10% CGB	$57.6 \pm 0.5 / 93.3 \pm 1.0$	114.3 ± 0.4	48.0 ± 2.4
20% CGB	$57.4 \pm 0.2 / 93.7 \pm 0.1$	113.4 ± 0.5	47.5 ± 5.3
40% CGB	$56.6 \pm 0.1 / 93.0 \pm 0.3$	113.3 ± 0.4	53.3 ± 4.2
2% CGSL	$58.0 \pm 0.5 / 93.7 \pm 0.8$	113.6 ± 0.5	47.5 ± 2.7
5% CGSL	$57.8 \pm 0.3 / 94.0 \pm 0.5$	113.2 ± 0.3	46.4 ± 3.5
10% CGSL	$57.7 \pm 0.4 / 93.1 \pm 0.6$	113.9 ± 0.5	48.3 ± 2.4
20% CGSL	$57.7 \pm 0.5 / 93.6 \pm 0.2$	113.8 ± 0.1	51.3 ± 2.2
40% CGSL	$57.8 \pm 0.1 / 93.5 \pm 0.1$	113.3 ± 0.7	49.8 ± 1.3
2% CGSL+E	$58.2 \pm 0.1 / 93.9 \pm 0.5$	113.7 ± 0.6	44.6 ± 5.1
5% CGSL+E	$57.6 \pm 0.4 / 93.9 \pm 0.4$	113.5 ± 0.2	45.1 ± 1.3
10% CGSL+E	$57.4 \pm 0.1 / 93.2 \pm 0.1$	113.8 ± 0.2	46.5 ± 2.5
20% CGSL+E	$57.3 \pm 0.3 / 93.1 \pm 0.1$	113.7 ± 0.1	48.2 ± 1.3
40% CGSL+E	$57.6 \pm 0.1 / 93.5 \pm 0.4$	113.4 ± 0.5	54.0 ± 6.5

514 The thermogravimetric measurements (TGA) results are summarized as collective TG and DTG
515 graphs for LDPE and its composites in Fig. 8. Table 4 contains additional information on the
516 characteristic decomposition temperatures at 5, 10, 20, and 50% of mass loss, residue at 900
517 °C, and detailed information on DTG peaks. Samples of pure LDPE show a single-stage
518 decomposition process in the range of 380-510 °C, typical for this material (Aboulkas et al.,
519 2010; Al-Bayaty et al., 2020). The DTG curves exhibit one peak with a maximum of 486 °C.
520 In the case of the composite series, only a slight decrease in the maximum value is observed in
521 this temperature range, but there is no correlation between the filler content and the temperature
522 change. Therefore, it can be concluded that the presence of the filler did not adversely affect
523 the polyethylene pyrolysis mechanism. None of the composites show significant changes in
524 thermal stability up to 200 °C (Sliwa et al., 2012), i.e., the generally accepted temperature for
525 the processing of polyethylene and composites containing fillers of plant origin. So, it can be
526 assumed that these materials can be freely formed using commonly used processing techniques
527 in this temperature range without the risk of degradation phenomena that may lead to
528 deterioration of mechanical properties resulting from increased porosity originating from the
529 decomposition of CG-based filler components. The observed lower $T_{5\%}$ for composites with a
530 high degree of filling (20 wt% and above) remain in the range exceeding the applicable
531 temperature range for polyethylene processing, so it can be concluded that it will not adversely
532 affect its range of applicability described in terms of thermal stability.

533

534

Fig. 8. TG and DTG curves of PE and its composites with CGB, CGSL and CGSL+E.

535

536

537

538

539

Table 4. Thermal properties of LDPE and composites based on TGA.

Material	T _{5%}	T _{10%}	T _{20%}	T _{50%}	Residue [%]	DTG peak
	[°C]					[°C;%/min]
LDPE	437	450	462	477	-	487;-30.9
2% CGB	433	447	460	476	0.1	482; -29.6
5% CGB	428	449	462	478	0.4	484; -29.6
10% CGB	329	431	457	476	1.8	317; -0.6 483; -27.3
20% CGB	288	360	451	476	3.5	335; -0.9 483; -24.2
40% CGB	250	297	385	476	8.1	221; -0.8 331; -1.7 485; -19.7
2% CGSL	433	448	461	477	0.0	484; -30.4
5% CGSL	412	444	459	477	0.4	338; -0.4 483; -28.7
10% CGSL	350	438	459	477	1.3	338; -0.6 484; -27.5
20% CGSL	295	349	448	474	3.0	337; -1.2 481; -23.9
40% CGSL	263	304	374	472	6.5	338; -2.1 482; -19.4
2% CGSL+E	432	447	460	476	0.1	331; -0.2 481; -31.6
5% CGSL+E	420	445	460	477	0.3	330; -0.3 483; -29.0
10% CGSL+E	339	434	457	476	1.3	335; -0.6 485; -27.3
20% CGSL+E	277	328	442	475	4.6	334; -1.5 481; -24.1
40% CGSL+E	241	277	328	417	11.1	232; -1.1 293; -1.8 335; -2.9 484; -15.7

541

542 The oxidation resistance of the polyethylene and its' composites was determined concerning
543 oxidation induction time, the values of which are listed in Table 5, where an extremely short
544 OIT is found for unmodified LDPE. Therefore, the measurements were based on the

545 methodology and guidelines that Schmid and Affolter (Schmid and Affolter, 2003)
 546 recommended for low-stable oxidation materials. The literature describes a correlation between
 547 OIT and increased resistance to aging, including that induced by radiation, including UV light
 548 (Dolgopolsky et al., 1997; Lungulescu et al., 2022; Sen and Basfar, 1998). Referring to the
 549 favorable changes in the oxidation resistance of composites containing fillers from all three
 550 series originating from the CG, an additional analysis of changes in selected groups of
 551 properties of these materials was carried out and described in the later part of this study.
 552 Referring to the results of the antioxidant activity of the fillers themselves (Table 1), the reduced
 553 activity noted in the case of CGSL+E was also transferred to the shorter OIT in the case of
 554 composites prepared using it. However, it should be emphasized that even in the case of this
 555 filler, a significant increase in resistance to melt oxidation was achieved.

556 **Table 5.** Oxidation induction time of PE and its composites with CGB, CGSL, and CGSL+E.

Oxidation induction time (OIT) [min]			
LDPE	0.5		
Filler content [wt%]	CGB	CGSL	CGSL+E
2	2.9	2.6	1.3
5	3.4	7.5	3.7
10	34.3	13.8	9.2
20	89.3	92.3	62.7
40	178.5	231.0	139.7

557

558 3.3. Stability of CG-filled composites to UV-light exposure

559 Reported the possibility of using CG as sustainable pigments, with the confirmed thermal
 560 stability of flavonoid dye based on quercetin exceeding 245 °C (Nguyen and Bechtold, 2021),
 561 the discoloration resistance in the presence of rich in active compounds fillers based on these
 562 plants was also verified by analysis of color change in CIELab coordinates (Table 6). The color
 563 analysis includes the evaluation of chromatic parameters (L^* , a^* , b^*), hue (h°), and chroma (C)
 564 for fillers. The polyethylene and composite samples were additionally supplemented by the

565 determination of total color change (ΔE) calculated according to Eq. (4) and browning index
566 (BI) as markers and degradation quality assessment color-related parameters.

567 Hue is the important parameter distinguished by color theory and is represented quantitatively
568 by a single number related to an angular position around a central or neutral point or axis on a
569 color space coordinate diagram. The determination of h° for fillers is related to the frequent use
570 of this parameter in the identification of biomass (Jiang and Nakano, 2021; Sass et al., 2012).
571 As described by Sass et al. (Sass et al., 2012), by correlating hue with the content of chlorophylls
572 in the leaves, this parameter allowed, in the considered case, to quantitatively define changes
573 caused by immersion in ethanol-water extract, which is comparable to bleaching. CGSL
574 modification resulted in a decrease in the hue value, which, taking into account the change in
575 color and results (Sass et al., 2012), may be coordinated with the partial removal of chlorophyll
576 from ground stems and leaves despite its' low solubility in methanol used as a solvent. The
577 higher a^* value for the CGSL+E series compared to untreated CGSL indicates a reduction in
578 the intensity of the green color, which is consistent with the measured h° values and the
579 assignment to the mentioned effect. The lower h° was previously correlated with the potential
580 release of anthocyanins from pomace powder by Nemetz et al. (Nemetz et al., 2021), who
581 suggest that this parameter in the considered case may be successfully used as a qualitative
582 measure for extractives removal by additional modification to which CGSL+E was subjected.
583 The higher C of CGSL is justified by the yellow color of the inflorescences, which, even after
584 drying and mechanical processing, were characterized by a more intense color resulting from
585 the presence of a higher content of quercitrin in inflorescences than in leaves (Radusiene et al.,
586 2015).

587 ΔE parameter or composites was determined for the same series before and after exposure to
588 UV light. It can be noticed that the most remarkable discoloration was recorded for
589 compositions containing 40 wt% CGB. For all composites, the color change exceeds the value

590 of 2, equivalent to medium color variations recognizable by an experienced observer (Bociaga
 591 and Trzaskalska, 2016). The gradual increase in CGB discoloration, which correlates with the
 592 increased filler content in this case, is probably due to the change in the color of the filler itself
 593 and the degree of absorption of light radiation caused by the darkening of the composites and
 594 the intensification of degradation (Stark and Matuana, 2003). Composites containing CGSL+E
 595 turned out to be the least sensitive to color changes, which can be attributed to the lowest color
 596 saturation and high initial brightness of the filler itself.

597

598 **Table 6.** The results of colorimetric analysis of composites components and LDPE-based
 599 composites before and after 100 h exposure to UV light.

Fillers	L*	a*	b*	C	h°
CGB	59.97	3.65	32.49	32.75	96.60
CGSL	63.72	-1.82	27.85	27.91	93.73
CGSL+E	64.41	4.38	26.90	27.25	80.75

Polymeric samples	-	Before aging				After aging			
	ΔE	L*	a*	b*	BI	L*	a*	b*	BI
LDPE	1.09	63.59	0.82	3.43	0.95	64.40	0.56	4.11	0.66
2% CGB	4.32	42.37	11.00	28.24	18.13	45.23	11.15	25.00	17.22
5% CGB	3.20	36.80	9.47	23.10	17.98	38.93	10.30	20.86	18.40
10% CGB	3.72	39.12	10.66	27.18	18.97	40.23	12.01	23.90	20.63
20% CGB	6.11	24.23	9.87	16.01	27.61	30.13	9.64	14.43	21.99
40% CGB	8.70	23.72	10.49	15.35	29.77	29.76	7.98	9.61	18.55
2% CGSL	4.69	47.88	7.97	25.24	11.88	51.28	8.29	22.02	11.49
5% CGSL	6.52	36.70	8.33	23.96	15.95	41.71	12.49	24.32	20.70
10% CGSL	6.40	40.43	3.76	23.47	6.84	41.16	10.11	23.06	17.17
20% CGSL	4.48	29.33	6.65	21.08	15.98	31.10	10.62	20.00	23.45
40% CGSL	5.63	36.12	6.99	23.25	13.72	39.13	11.71	23.86	20.69
2% CGSL+E	3.00	41.51	4.22	17.41	7.58	40.03	6.67	16.50	11.82
5% CGSL+E	4.89	34.63	7.57	21.60	15.40	37.95	11.16	21.63	20.34
10% CGSL+E	5.86	32.21	7.84	19.40	17.02	37.48	9.77	17.71	18.13
20% CGSL+E	2.85	28.34	7.35	18.08	18.11	30.22	9.13	16.89	20.88
40% CGSL+E	2.69	28.25	7.78	19.33	19.19	29.01	9.92	17.88	23.47

600

601 Fig. 9 shows the FTIR spectra for LDPE and composites containing three types of filler obtained
602 from CG after exposure to UV light provided by accelerated aging using a Xenon lamp. The
603 spectra reveal characteristic absorption bands for the polymeric matrix corresponding to
604 symmetric and asymmetric stretching of C-H bonds at 2913 and 2845 cm^{-1} , wagging and
605 twisting deformations at 1100-1366 cm^{-1} , bending deformations of C-H bonds at 1466 cm^{-1} ,
606 and rocking vibrations of macromolecules in the range of 720-732 cm^{-1} (Favaro et al., 2010;
607 Gulmine et al., 2002). In all composite samples, an additional absorption band, dependent on
608 the filler concentration, is observed with a peak at 3360 cm^{-1} , corresponding to the hydroxyl
609 groups (OH) present in the hydrophilic lignocellulosic filler (Liew et al., 2018).
610 Exposure to intense radiation usually results in the formation of several new bonds caused by
611 photooxidation of the polyethylene, including vinylidene (888 cm^{-1}), terminal vinyl (909 cm^{-1}),
612 trans-vinylene (965 cm^{-1}), ketones (1715 cm^{-1}), esters (1730 cm^{-1}), anhydrides (1770 cm^{-1})
613 (Martínez-Romo et al., 2015). The most visible changes caused by light radiation exposure are
614 carbonyl groups forming in the 1800-1600 cm^{-1} range (Gajdošová et al., 2021; Martínez-Romo
615 et al., 2015). According to Eq. (3), based on their intensity, carbonyl index values were
616 determined, quantifying the oxidation level of the samples and described later.

617

618

619

620 **Fig. 9.** FTIR spectra of LDPE and its' composites after 100 h exposure to UV light.

621

622 The carbonyl index (CI) values determined based on FTIR spectra before and after exposure to
 623 UV light are summarized in Table 7. Based on the results obtained, it can be concluded that
 624 introducing fillers from various parts of plants causes differentiated stabilization effects. In the
 625 case of CGSL, all values are below those obtained for pure LDPE. The lowest value was
 626 recorded for 40 wt% CGSL. In the case of material containing inflorescences, a beneficial effect
 627 of the filler is observed at the lowest concentrations; however, the CI values above 10 wt% were
 628 increased by more than twice. Considering the previously discussed OIT results, it can be
 629 concluded that in the case of CGB, the effect of UV radiation does not correlate with the OIT

630 results, indicating a very complex course of the degradation process. This may be related to the
 631 most intense color change (ΔE) of these samples with increased filler content, which led to
 632 progressively increasing absorption of UV radiation, exceeding the beneficial stabilizing effects
 633 resulting from the phytochemicals contained in the fillers. Modification of the filler based on
 634 ground CG leaves and stems using the extract was characterized by a lack of noticeably
 635 beneficial effects compared to CGSL. In the case of CGSL and CGSL+E, no correlation is
 636 observed between the filler and CI values, which may be due to the lower heterogeneity of the
 637 samples themselves or the complex and mutually exclusive effects of catalytic and stabilizing
 638 LDPE degradation occurring during exposure to UV-light.

639

640 **Table 7.** Carbonyl index (CI) based on FTIR spectra analysis after 100 h UV light radiation
 641 for LDPE and its composites with CGB, CGSL, and CGSL+E.

CI [-]			
LDPE	0.64		
Filler content [wt%]	CGB	CGSL	CGSL+E
2	0.36	0.37	0.50
5	0.31	0.44	0.65
10	0.52	0.56	0.34
20	1.38	0.40	0.37
40	1.55	0.32	0.56

642

643 The confirmed increased resistance to oxidation of polyethylene composites caused by
 644 introducing fillers originating from CG into its structure was subject to analysis of mechanical
 645 properties and color changes after exposure to UV light and supplemented with spectroscopic
 646 analysis. The results of measurements of mechanical properties were determined in a static
 647 tensile test. The results summarized in Fig. 10 show the variations of elastic modulus, tensile
 648 strength, and elongation at break as a function of the amount of the filler before and after
 649 exposure to 100 h radiation in controlled conditions. When comparing the mechanical

650 properties of unaged samples, changes are typical for thermoplastic polymer composites
651 modified with lignocellulosic fillers (Fu et al., 2008; Tajvidi and Ebrahimi, 2003). The
652 increasing share of the above three fillers resulted in an increase in elastic modulus along with
653 a decrease in tensile strength and a significant limitation of elongation at break. The stiffness of
654 the composites up to 10 wt% was comparable to pure LDPE, while a further increase in the
655 share of fillers resulted in a noticeable increase in E and diversification between series, most
656 clearly revealed by the 40 wt%-filled series. The sample containing CGSL+E had the highest
657 stiffness, reaching a threefold increase compared to pure LDPE (from 177 to 523 MPa). The
658 tensile strength of composite samples gradually decreased with increasing filler content
659 compared to the LDPE sample. The most significant reduction of this mechanical parameter
660 was observed at the highest concentration for CGB and CGSL composites, a comparable
661 reduction in value for those composite series to a level approaching ~4.9 MPa, which is 50%
662 of the reference sample.

663 Temperature or UV-light-induced oxidation of polyethylene increases its stiffness (Hsueh et al.,
664 2020), which may be caused by the accompanying cross-linking effects (Rodriguez et al., 2020).
665 Materials with the highest concentration of fillers were characterized by the lowest lightness
666 (L^*) values, which, as shown in the literature, were more capable of absorbing UV radiation
667 (Stark and Matuana, 2003). At the same time, the increasing share of plant-derived fillers is
668 usually associated with reduced thermal conductivity of the materials, which could intensify
669 the oxidation processes of polyethylene composites.

670 The elastic modulus of the composites containing 40 wt% CGB and CGSL increased
671 significantly after exposure, which can be connected with the limited stabilizing effectiveness
672 of active compounds contained in blossoms compared to leaves and stems. This effect may be
673 confirmed by the discussed CI results, for which the CGSL and CGSL+E composites were
674 characterized by CI values comparable and lower than those of CGB.

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678

679 **Fig. 10.** Tensile test results for LDPE and its' composites before and after UV light radiation.

680

681 4. Conclusions

682 The screen research on the use of Canadian goldenrod as an active filler for the production of
683 polyethylene composites allowed for obtaining comprehensive data, directing further
684 possibilities for processing biomass from this invasive plant. The fillers made of fragmented
685 blossoms (CGB), stems, and leaves (CGSL) provide additional functionality of composites
686 (increased oxidation stability). The methodology of modifying stems and leaves by immersion
687 in the blossom extract (CGSL+E) did not provide the expected synergistic effect of
688 oversaturation by phytochemicals, probably due to the partial extraction of active ingredients
689 contained in the modified filler itself. However, this raises several questions and opens a new
690 direction in searching for ways to modify and maximize the use of all parts of the CG.

691 All fillers increased the polyethylene resistance to oxidation, confirmed by calorimetric tests
692 (DSC-OIT) and spectroscopic analyses of the samples after UV radiation. The beneficial
693 mechanical effect of CG was achieved in the case of composites with a high filler content (>20
694 wt%). The presence of stiff fractions of the ground plant resulted in increased stiffness, but also,
695 after the process of radiation exposure, the Young modulus of composites with high filler
696 content increased to a level almost twice as high as in the case of the sample before exposure
697 while maintaining an acceptable tensile strength. The lack of correlation between OIT and CI
698 (FTIR) description of the composite oxidation process and changes in tensile strength are
699 caused by the complexity of composite structure interactions. Changes in mechanical properties
700 could be partially related to the effect of radiation absorption by the materials, which were
701 initially darker due to a high amount of filler.

702 The use of Canadian goldenrod as a functional filler of polyethylene composites is justified,
703 and the obtained effect allows the newly obtained materials to be classified as composites with
704 "self-stabilizing" properties. It is possible to increase their resistance to oxidizing sources and,

705 in effect, exclude or reduce the use of additional light stabilizers, improving the sustainability
706 of these materials.

707

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709 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal
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723 The authors declare they did not use generative AI systems while preparing and writing the
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725

726 **Competing Interests**

727 The authors have no relevant financial or non-financial interests to disclose.

728

729

730 **Ethics approval and consent to participate**

731 Not applicable.

732

733 **Consent for publication**

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735

736 **Author Contributions**

737 The study conception and design: MB, JA; Material preparation: MB, JA, LS, KS;
738 Investigations, data collection and analysis: MB, JA, KS, ZO, LS, AH; The first draft of the
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740 confirm that the final manuscript version has been read and approved by all of the co-authors.

741

742 **Data Availability**

743 The datasets generated during and/or analyzed during the current study are available from the
744 corresponding author upon reasonable request.

745

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